

Criteria Catalog for Cross-Sectional Examination in Business 2018/19

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NOTE: This is not a professional translation and is probably not accurate. I used Google Translate and manually edited the resulting text.

1 Preparation for the GDPR

How did you prepare as a company for the GDPR? Describe (briefly) the procedure, which areas were involved and which measures were initiated. If not all Fully implemented, please also explain the implementation status.

Note: The purpose of this question was to provide an overview of the different approaches of the companies as well as their self-assessment regarding their position on the market Road to implementation DS-GVO. An evaluation of the methodology does not explicitly take place.

- 1 Is there any significant involvement of any significant business units that work with personal data (e.g., human resources, IT, sales / customer care, marketing)?
- 2 Is there evidence that training on the GDPR has been carried out?
- 3 Have all measures planned by the company been implemented?

2 List of processing activities (VVT)

How did you ensure that all your personal data processing operations were included in a list of processing activities? How do you ensure its timeliness? Please provide an overview of your documented procedures and a sample procedure as a sample.

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¹https://lfd.niedersachsen.de/download/146715/Kriterienkatalog_zur_Querschnittspruefung_in_der_Wirtschaft_2018_19.pdf

²<https://www.technologylawdispatch.com/2019/08/privacy-data-protection/german-dpa-released-audit-checklist-for-gdpr-readiness/>

Art. 30 DS-GVO

- 1 Have existing procedures been adapted to the new legal situation or new procedures been implemented?
- 2 Is the list of processing activities (VVT) regularly reviewed and updated as necessary?
- 3 Does the process overview show that the standard methods for e.g. office communication, personnel administration, payroll, application management, homepage and customer administration are documented?
- 4 Does the submitted model procedure comply with the legal requirements of Art. 30 (1) GDPR?
 - a Are the name and contact details of the responsible person indicated?
 - b Are - as far as applicable - the name and contact details of the person responsible indicated?
 - c Are - as far as applicable - name and contact details of the representative of the person responsible indicated?
 - d Are - as far as applicable - name and contact details of the possibly existing data protection officer indicated?
 - e Are the purposes of processing indicated?
 - f Are the categories of affected persons (e.g., employees, customers, etc.) and categories of personal data (e.g., employee master data, applicant data, customer contact information, credit data, etc.) described?
 - g Are the categories of beneficiaries (e.g., banks, social security funds, corporate data receivers such as works council or doctor) against whom the personal data has been disclosed or yet to be disclosed identified?
 - h Is there transfer of personal data to a third country or to an internal organization?
 - i Are deadlines for deletion of the various categories of data specified?
 - j Is there a general description of the technical & organizational measures acc. Art. 32 para. 1 GDPR?

3 Admissibility of processing

Based on which legal bases do you process personal data? If you also process personal data on the basis of consent, please enclose your samples.

Art. 6, 7 and 8 DS-GVO

- 1 Are the mentioned legal bases plausible on the basis of the submitted procedure overview?

- 2 Is the declaration of consent easy to understand, i.e. is the consent of the person concerned showing the "whether" and "how" of giving consent in a clear and simple language?
- 3 Is the identity of the person responsible indicated?
- 4 Is the purpose of processing indicated?
- 5 Is the type of data that is collected and used indicated?
- 6 Is the right of withdrawal noted?
- 7 Is it apparent from the documents that the revocation is as easy as the granting of consent?
- 8 Is there evidence that the characteristic of voluntariness could be missing?
- 9 Is it clear from the documents that the consent is documented?

4 Affected rights

How do you ensure compliance with the data subject rights (on information, provision of information, correction, deletion, Limitation of processing, data portability)? Document your relevant processes and, in particular, detail how you comply with your information obligations. Please enclose existing sample information.

Art. 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20 DS-GVO

- 1 Information according to Art. 13 and 14 (sample):
 - a Has the processing of the information obligation been comprehensible and described in relation to the company (for example, in an internal action guide specifically related to the company)?
 - b Is the information made readily available (such as notice, flyer, email, letter ...)?
 - c Is the information clearly presented (for example, by headings, paragraphs, outline)?
 - d Is the information understandable and formulated in simple language? (no ambiguity, avoidance of specialized vocabulary, subject vocabulary used becomes, explanation of the technical terms)
 - e If the data subjects are informed about the controller (name and contact details)?
 - f Does it indicate the contact details of the DSB?
 - g Does it inform about the purpose of the processing and gives the legal basis?
 - h If legitimate interest is described, provided that processing is pursuant to Art. 6 para. 1 Letter f. GDPR is done?
 - i Are the recipient or categories of recipients of personal information described?

- j Does it inform the person responsible about the transmission or intention of a transmission of personal data to a third country or an international organization?
- k If i. applies: Does it inform the person responsible about the presence or absence adequacy decision of the Commission or, in the case of transfers pursuant to Article 46 or 47 or 49 (1) of the GDPR, of the appropriate or appropriate guarantees and the possibility of obtaining a copy from them or where they are available?
- l Is information when collecting the data about the storage duration?
- m Is reference made to the right to information?
- n Is the right to rectification informed?
- o Is the right to delete informed?
- p Is reference made to the right to restrict processing?
- q Is the right of objection informed?
- r Is the right to data portability informed?
- s Is the right to revoke consent indicated?
- t Is the right to complaint the supervisory authority indicated?
- u Is reference made to the legal or contractual obligation for processing (legal basis)?
- v If there is an automated decision-making process (e.g., profiling), is information provided about the logic involved and its implications for the affected person?
- w In the event of an intended change of purpose, is it ensured that the data subject receives information about this other purpose and all other relevant information (see points l to v above) before further processing?
- x Is there a privacy policy on the site?
- y Is the privacy policy easy to find (max 2 clicks from the start page)?
- z Is the privacy policy understandable and in plain language? (Definition see point (d))

2 Right to information

- a Is the handling of the right to information plausible and logically comprehensible and described in relation to the company (for example, in an internal action guide specifically related to the company)?
- b Is it described that the identity of the natural person is verified as the person affected?
- c Is it clear from the process described that the information will be given promptly, and in any event within one month of receipt of the application?
- d Can the process description reveal that the controller is expected to provide complete information (for example, by describing the federated business units, reference to the use of a software application)? Note: Complete information must cover the following content:

- all processing purposes
 - all categories of processed personal data
 - all recipients or categories of recipients to whom the personal data have been disclosed or are yet to be disclosed
 - all recipients in third countries or int. Organizations
 - the planned storage period or, if this information is not possible, the criteria for determining the storage duration
 - the existence of a right of appeal to a supervisory authority
- e Is it apparent from the documents that the person responsible provides a copy of the personal data on request?

3 Right of rectification

- a Is the handling of the right to rectify comprehensible and has been described in relation to the company (for example, in an internal action guide specifically related to the company)?
- b Is it described that the identity of the natural person as the affected person is checked?
- c Is it clear from the described process that the affected person will be informed immediately without delay, but in any case within one month after receipt of the application?
- d Is it apparent from the documents that the person responsible, insofar as he has disclosed the data to other recipients, informs all recipients of any correction?

4 Deletion

- a Is the handling of the right to erasure comprehensible and has been described in relation to the company (for example, in an internal action guide specifically related to the company)?
- b Is it described that the identity of the natural person as the affected person is checked?
- c Is it clear from the described process that the affected person will be informed immediately without delay, but in any case within one Month after receipt of the application?
- d Is it described under what conditions data is deleted? Note: Data deletion is required in the following cases:
- if the storage of the data is no longer necessary
 - if the consent is revoked, unless otherwise provided for Processing
 - in case of opposition to the processing acc. Art. 21 para. 1 GDPR and non-submission of superior legitimate reasons or in case of opposition to the processing gem. Art. 21 (2) GDPR (Advertising Contest)

- in case of unlawful processing (processing of data without legal basis)
 - as far as the deletion is necessary to fulfill a legal obligation
- e Is it apparent from the documents that the person responsible, insofar as he has disclosed the data to other recipients, notifies all recipients of any deletion?

5 Restrictions of processing

- a Is the handling of the right to restriction of processing comprehensible and been described in relation to the company (e.g., in an internal, concrete, on the company related action guide)? Note: Processing must be restricted in the following cases:
- if the accuracy of the processed data is in dispute, as long as the accuracy of the Data is checked
 - in the event of unlawful processing, in so far as the data subject refuses to delete them and requests that processing be restricted
 - if the data controller no longer uses the data for the purposes of processing however, the data subject requires them to assert, exercise or defend legal claims
 - in case of opposition of the data subject acc. Art. 21 para. 1 GDPR, until it is established whether the legitimate reasons of the data subject or the person responsible prevail
- b Is it described that the identity of the natural person as the affected person is checked?
- c Does it emerge from the process described that the data subject is informed without delay, and in any event within one month of receipt of the application, of the measures taken (restriction of processing)?
- d Is it described that the data subject is informed of the restriction as well as of the termination of the cancellation?
- e Is it apparent from the documents that the person responsible, insofar as he has disclosed the data to other recipients, informs all recipients of any restriction?

6 Data portability

- a Is the handling of the right to data portability comprehensible and described in relation to the Company (for example, in an internal action guide specifically related to the company)?
- b Is it described that the identity of the natural person as the affected person is checked?
- c Is it clear from the process described that the data subject is informed immediately, but in any case within one month of receipt of the application?
- d Is it described that the person responsible for the data transferability ensures that the data is provided in a standard, structured and machine-readable format (i.e., easily identifiable, extracted, and opened by a common software application)?

5 technical data protection

5.1 a. How do you ensure that your technical and organizational measures or those of your service providers guarantee a level of protection appropriate to the processing risk?

Art. 32 DS-BER

- 1 Is a risk-based approach included in the response?
- 2 Has it been shown to have been understood that based on the risk identified the stated technical and organizational measures are suitable for reducing risk to adequate level of protection?
- 3 Does the answer indicate that it has been understood that a consideration process (risk, Implementation costs and state of the art) must be carried in order to achieve an adequate level of protection?
- 4 Does the answer indicate that the company has realized that responsibility for the service provider's technical and organizational measures remains with the person responsible?

5.2 b. How do you make sure that your technical and organizational measures are adapted to the respective State of the art?

Art. 32 (1) (d) of the GDPR

Note: The prior art refers to the best possible marketable techniques that currently have a high safety standard, even if their use has not (yet) become established in practice. In individual cases, the requirement is limited by the fact that only the technically feasible is required. As a result of the technical change, the selection decision must again be taken if new technical measures are available. The classification is thus to be understood dynamically. At the bottom, the state of the art is differentiated from the "accepted rules of technology" (for example, DIN standards), and upwards from the "state of science and technology" (latest technical and scientific findings).

- 1 Has the term "state of the art" been understood correctly?
- 2 Does the answer indicate that it has been understood that the company must prove that the the technical and organizational measures take into consideration the state of the art?
- 3 Does the answer indicate that it has been understood that the "state of the art" continues to evolve?
- 4 Does the answer indicate that it has been understood that the technical-organizational measures must continuously take into account the respective "state of the art"?

c

5.3 How do you ensure that you have a documented data protection compliant role and authorization concept for the IT applications you currently or in the future use?

Art. 32 (1) (b) DS-BER

- 1 Does the answer show that it has been understood that the knowledge and consideration of the organization is relevant for the rights and roles concept?
- 2 Does the answer show that it has been understood that separation of functions and the separation of person and role must be taken into account?
- 3 Does the answer show that it has been understood that the documentation of the authorized users and rights profiles must be taken into account in the rights and roles concept?
- 4 Does the answer show that it has been understood that the selection of identity and authorization management systems must be taken into account in the rights and roles concept?

5.4 d. How do you ensure that data protection requirements are taken into account right from the start when changing or redeveloping products or services (Privacy by Design and by Default)?

Art. 25 DS-GVO

- 1 Does the answer show that it has been understood that privacy should be considered as the default?
- 2 Does the answer show that it has been understood that privacy must be respected throughout the lifecycle?
- 3 Does the answer show that it has been understood that the aim is to minimize the processing of personal data?
- 4 Does the answer show that it has been understood that transparency should be established with regard to functions and the Processing of personal data?

6 Privacy Impact Assessment

6.1 a. How do you ensure that processing with a likely high risk to the rights and freedoms of those affected is detected and carried out a privacy impact assessment?

Art. 35 DS-GVO

- 1 Will all standards requiring high risk affirmation checked?

- a Art. 35 para. 4?
 - b Art. 35 para. 3?
 - c Art. 35 para. 1?
- 2 Which methods are used for risk determination?
- a WP 248?
 - b KP No. 18 - Risk?
 - c Own method?
 - d Is the own method described suitable for identifying high-risk procedures?
- 3 Is it described who is responsible for the evaluation?
- 4 Is it described where the threshold check is documented?
- b

6.2 Do you have processing in your company that is likely to be at high risk? Rights and freedoms of those affected identified? Which? Please include the respective documentation for the Privacy Impact Assessment.

Art. 35, 36 DS-GVO

- 1 Which DPIA was evaluated as an example?
- 2 Have procedures with likely high risks to rights and freedoms of natural Persons been identified by the person responsible?
- 3 Content audit capability
- a Is there a systematic description of the processing operations?
 - b Is there a systematic description of the processing purposes?
 - c Result
- 4 Did a DPIA have to be made for the present form of processing?
- a Yes
 - b No, because no high risk
 - c No, because a DPIA has already been done for a similar process
 - d No, because the processing started before 25 May 2018 and the Data Protection Supervisor or the Data Protection Supervisor examined the procedure as part of a prior check and the risks have not changed since then
- 5 Is there an assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing operations for the purpose?

- a Is the need for processing claimed?
 - b Is the need justified?
 - c Is the proportionality of the processing operations claimed?
 - d Is the proportionality of the processing operations justified?
- 6 Is there an assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects?
- a Is the risk assessment method described?
 - b How much of the following warranty objectives are considered: confidentiality, integrity, availability, transparency, intervenability, non-chaining
 - c Are risks named?
 - d Is the severity of the damage stated?
 - e Are the classifications of the seriousness of the damage justified?
 - f Is the probability of occurrence stated?
 - g Are the classifications of the probabilities of occurrence justified?
 - h Does the justification take into account the nature, extent, circumstances and purposes of the processing?
 - i Are sources of risk named? For example, Hackers, hardware failure, own employees
- 7 remedies
- a Are remedies called?
 - b Are the remedies described?
 - c Do the remedies address the identified risks?
 - d Do the remedies account for the implementation costs?
 - e Do the remedies reflect the state of the art?
 - f Is there a residual risk assessment?
- 8 Has it been examined whether to conduct a prior consultation procedure under Article 36?
- 9 Has the council of the Data Protection Officer been obtained pursuant to Article 35 (2)?
- 10 Has the position of the data subjects been obtained pursuant to Article 35 (9)?

7 Order processing

Have you adapted your existing contracts with processors to the new regulations of the GDPR? If you use model contracts, please attach them, in addition please add a current sample contract with one of your processors.

Art. 28 DS-GMO

- 1 Is it clear from the documents that the existing contracts have been adapted to the new legal situation?
- 2 Does the submitted sample meet the legal requirements?
 - a Is the object of processing specified in the contract?
 - b Is the duration of the agreement fixed?
 - c Does the contract contain information on the nature (modalities such as collection, organization, adaptation, dissemination or destruction of data) and purpose of processing?
 - d Were the type of personal data and the categories of data subjects set?
 - e Is there a documentation of the authority of the responsible person?
 - f Is there a regulation regarding the transfer of personal data to a third country or to an international organization?
 - g Does the model contract ensure that the persons authorized to process the personal data have undertaken to maintain confidentiality? (for example, by assurances that there is a commitment under Art. 29 is present)
 - h Is there a rule according to which the processor takes necessary technical and organizational measures w.r.t. Art. 32 GDPR?
 - i Has the model contract stipulated that the use of another processor is subject to the prior approval of the person in charge or a ban on subcontracting has been agreed?
 - j In the case of subcontracting, has it been arranged that the subcontractor is to impose the same obligations as the processor?
 - k Does the model contract contain a rule according to which the processor supports the person responsible in implementing the data subjects' rights?
 - l Does the model contract include a provision according to which the processor shall assist those responsible in complying with the obligations set out in Articles 32 to 36?
 - m Have the obligations of the processor been fixed after the order/processing has been completed (at the discretion of the person responsible for deletion or return of all personal data)?
 - n Have the control rights of the person responsible been determined?
- 3 Does the sample contract sent meet the legal requirements?
 - a Has the object of processing been specified in the contract?
 - b Has the duration of the agreement been fixed?
 - c Does the contract contain information on the nature and purpose of the processing?
 - d Have the type of personal data and categories of data subjects been defined?
 - e Is there a documentation of the authority of the responsible person?

- f Is there a regulation regarding the transfer of personal data to a third country or an international organization?
- g Does the sample contract ensure that the persons authorized to process the personal data have committed themselves to confidentiality? (for example, by assurances that there is a commitment under Art. 29 is present)
- h Is there a rule according to which the processor takes necessary technical and organizational measures w.r.t. Art. 32 GDPR?
- i If the example contract stipulates that the use of another order processor requires prior approval of the person in charge or a ban on Subcontracting has been agreed?
- j In the case of subcontracting, has it been arranged that the subcontractor is to impose the same obligations as the processor?
- k Does the sample contract contain a provision under which the processor supports the person responsible in implementing the data subject rights?
- l Does the example contract include a provision under which the processor supports those responsible in complying with the obligations set out in Articles 32 to 36?
- m Have the obligations of the processor been fixed after the order/processing has been completed (At the discretion of the person responsible for deletion or return of all personal data)?
- n Have the control rights of the person responsible been determined?

8 Data Protection Officer

How is your privacy officer involved in your organization? Which expert certificate do they possess?

Art. 37, 38 DS-GVO

- 1 Organizational integration with an internal DPO:
 - a The company data protection officer DPO reports directly in his function to the executive/management?
 - b Does the DPO still have a line task in the company?
 - c If so, what position is still held in the company?
 - d Is this a danger of bias and thus a conflict of interest? (For example, DPO is owner, board, executive or HR or IT director)
- 2 Organizational involvement with an external DPO: Is there a risk of bias and thus a conflict of interest? (For example, because the named DPO is still a service provider for IT Services to the company)
- 3 Can the current and sufficient knowledge of the DPO be taken from the documents? In the evaluation of the subject flow e.g. education and training in data protection, Scope

of experience (duration) in data protection, vocational training (eg lawyer, computer scientist), participation in established data protection networks (eg Erfa-Kreis, GDD, BvD)

- 4 Publication of the contact details of the DPO:
 - a Did the publication take place on the company's website?
 - b Is the contact information of the DPO easy to find there? (max 2 clicks from the start page)
- 5 Did a DPO report to the supervisory authority?

9 Reporting obligations

How to make sure your business reports data breaches in due time to the regulator reports? Sketch your relevant processes.

Art. 33, 34 DS-GVO

- 1 Is the process of reporting privacy violations comprehensible?
- 2 Are the responsibilities (who is doing what) clearly regulated in the notification process?
- 3 Is the 72-hour deadline recognizable?
- 4 Is it clear that the employees have been sensitized to this process?
- 5 Is it apparent from the documents that the data protection violations are documented?

10 Documentation

How can you ensure compliance with all of the above in para. 2 - 9 obligations?

Art. 5 para. 2 DS-GVO

Does the answer or the other documents show that there is documentation for each of the queried obligations?